

Still life composition of different objects work in the background of the country.

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Annotation

In this article, information is collected on the composition of a still life composed of various materials against a contrasting background. A still life composed of contrasting colors can be a little complicated, but if it is done properly and drawn according to the rules, it can be a real work of art. Basically, such types are drawn in higher education institutions. In this type of still life, more attention is paid to the color technique. Through this article, I have written my knowledge and skills on still life on a country background. The main goal is to be able to show correct placement, correct coloring, and color harmony.

Keywords: Contrast, background, composition, color technique, still life, geometric objects, achromatic, chromatic grayscale, cylindrical object.

Аннотация

В данной статье собрана информация о композиции натюрморта, составленного из различных материалов на контрастном фоне. Натюрморт, составленный из контрастных цветов, может быть немного сложным, но если он выполнен правильно и нарисован по правилам, то может стать настоящим произведением искусства. В основном такие типы рисуются в высших учебных заведениях. В этом виде натюрморта больше внимания уделяется цветовой технике. В этой статье я изложил свои знания и навыки в области натюрморта на деревенском фоне. Основная цель состоит в том, чтобы показать правильное размещение, правильную окраску и цветовую гармонию.

Ключевые слова: Контраст, фон, композиция, цветовая техника, натюрморт, геометрические объекты, ахроматика, хроматическая градация серого, цилиндрический объект.

Correct placement of the still life on the paper surface, careful pencil drawing of objects, determining the proportions, finding the character and coloring. Making a painting taking into account the nature of color and color relationships and lighting characteristics. Follow a methodical sequence

It would not be wrong to say that studying its laws, methods and technology is one of the most important tasks in painting. It is natural that knowledge about achromatic and chromatic colors is included among such prerequisites. All colors in nature that our eyes can see can be conditionally divided into two: achromatic and chromatic colors. Colors from white to dark black belong to achromatic colors (white, gray, dark, black, dark black), and the rest belong to chromatic colors (red, yellow, blue, etc.). relations: the lightness of the background is determined in relation to the lightness of the objects on the surface and to each other. First of all, the general color of the items in the set is covered. If we get the general relations wrong, we will not be able to show the accuracy of the pencil drawing, the light and shadow in the voluminous forms of the next individual objects, the accuracy and truthfulness of the image, materiality and breadth. The work should be carried out from shadow to light, on top of that, it is necessary to give the shadow areas as thin and thin a layer of paint as possible, and to cover the light with a much darker layer of dark

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paint and clear strokes. while describing its appearance, its structural construction and proportions may be overlooked.

A still life composed of geometric shapes. The mutual location of things, the direction of the desired edge is easily determined in nature, and the image is easily built on paper with the help of vertical (vertical), horizontal (horizontal) lines of nature. With the help of a long pencil, it is possible to check the perspective angles of the device, the aspect ratios, and the places where they stand on the plane of the table. To do this, you can check the perspective direction of the edges by holding the pencil vertically, horizontally or at an angle with an outstretched hand.

Chromatic colors, in turn, are conditionally divided into two, warm and cold colors. Warm colors include fire, sun, red, yellow, golden colors that remind of the color of hot things. Cold colors are blue, blue, violet, reminiscent of the color of ice, air, water. Green and purple colors can sometimes be warm and sometimes cool. Because green is a mixture of yellow and blue. Purple is a mixture of red and blue. As you can see, these colors are formed from a mixture of warm and cold colors. When mixing, if the amount of warm color is more than the amount of cold color, the resulting color can go into the warm color range, and if the amount of cool color is more, it can go into the cool color range. Similarly, violet is considered warm when it has more red, and cool when it has more blue. So, in the training session, color-it is important to clearly show the light-shadow ratio of objects and objects in the composition, as well as the color ratio.

The naturalness of colors getting it right in an image is a much more difficult task. This can be achieved through hard work, fine taste and excellent observation. In order to learn to distinguish the degrees of hunger and satiety of things in a still life, to understand the unity of color in it, it is of great importance to depict a still life in one color. Painting in this way makes it much easier to move on to color rendering of difficult still lifes later. The method of writing in one color is called "grisaille".

Painting in the grisaille method is a preparatory stage for the transition to the method of working with different colors, which provides an opportunity to learn the ways of using a brush and the properties of watercolor paints. After learning how to depict several still lifes with this technique, it will be much easier to work with still lifes with all kinds of colors. In the grisaille technique, shadow, penumbra, reflexes are covered with suitable paints in the desired color at once, (paint as much as possible without repeating the application) it is necessary to move the paint smears in the direction of the form. For example, if a cylindrical object is rubbed in different random directions, it is difficult to show the circularity of this shape.

Still lifes are often placed in rooms. But sometimes it is necessary to describe it in the heart of nature. In such a case, it is important to analyze and understand the color characteristics of a still life before working on it. Because the light coming from the window gives cold colors to the still life placed inside the room. On the contrary, the shadows falling from the objects appear warm. Outdoors, outdoor subjects are the opposite, where the shadows may appear cold and the highlights warm. Observing such situations carefully and then carefully describing them will have an effect on the quality of the work.

Contrast (ing, Russian "contrast") means a sharp difference between two objects.

It should be noted that the emphasis is on the concept of sharp difference. A simple distinction is not understood here.

Let's take color contrast for example: There are 2 colors here. Be bold and be bold. We notice the difference between these colors. There is a difference in colors, but the contrast is poor. We do not say that the contrast is there or not, but that the contrast is strong or weak. It is true to say so. Because contrast here also refers to the word "difference".

There are no ready-made paints that determine the exact color of things in nature. But a mature artist can depict anything, taking into account their characteristics, perceiving the interaction of colors and their appearance. In order to achieve such attractiveness and realism in the image, the artist needs to know the ratio of colors, the different shades of one color between the colors. helped to take into account. For example, in order to depict the fire color red as burning more strongly, the shadow of the objects around this color is given in blue, green, bluish shades. In order for there to be complete similarity between what is being drawn and the image, there must also be similarity in their color ratios. To achieve this, it is necessary to deeply study the basics of color science and repeatedly refer to these issues in the practical work process. In order to depict still lifes with various paints (watercolor, gouache, watercolor), it is recommended to carry out the above-mentioned experiments, to get to know the technological features of paints, and to do many exercises to master the methods of their use. will be done.

C M R T

Summary:

In conclusion, it can be said that this article is a collection of instructional pictures and necessary information for students of fine arts and engineering graphics. The article shows the rules of still-life work and grayscale work, which are made up of sharply different colors.

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